

Kinetics of Silver Catalysed Oxidation of N-Methyl Acetamide by Potassium Peroxydisulphate

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The kinetics of silver catalysed oxidation of N-methyl acetamide by peroxydisulphate ion in aqueous medium has been investigated. The reaction is found to be first order w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$; zero order w.r.t. N-methyl acetamide but the specific rate is function of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $CH_3CONHCH_3$ concentrations. It decreases with an increase in $S_2O_8^{2-}$ concentration but increases with an increase in $CH_3CONHCH_3$ concentration and becomes immeasurable at high concentrations. The specific rate is linearly related to $[Ag^+]$ ion by an expression.

$$K = 3.60 \times 10^{-3} + 0.40 \times C_{Ag^+}$$

K^+ exerts a strong inhibitory effect on the rate. The temperature coefficient, energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation have been calculated. The molecular ratio is found to be 2 : 1. The final products of the system are CH_3COOH , CO_2 , N_2 and H_2O . On the basis of these results a possible reaction mechanism has been proposed and a corresponding rate expression has been deduced.

PEROXYDISULPHATE ion has only been used to bring about the oxidation of several classes of organic substrates and the kinetics of some of the processes have been dealt by different workers. These studies up to 1962 have been reviewed by House¹. The noteworthy work done may be cited as oxidation of oxalic acid²⁻⁴ and of alcohols⁵⁻⁸. However, only recently the kinetic study of oxidation of amides by peroxydisulphate ion has been carried out by Mushran and coworkers^{9,10} and by Srivastava and Singh¹¹⁻¹⁴. The present paper contains the results of kinetic study of silver catalysed oxidation of N-methyl acetamide by peroxydisulphate ion in an aqueous medium.

Experimental

The experimental technique of dimethyl formamide-peroxydisulphate reaction¹¹ has been adopted in this case as well. Blank estimation of peroxydisulphate ion in presence of N-methyl acetamide was first done to test the sensitivity of this method in this procedure.

Results

As in the reactions of dimethyl formamide¹¹ and propionamide¹² the specific rate (k) for N-methyl acetamide oxidation in each kinetic run was determined by subtracting the specific rate (k_a) for self decomposition of potassium peroxydisulphate, carried out under similar conditions from the rate (k_1) for the total reaction. The kinetic results obtained at various concentrations of reactants are given graphically in Figs. 1 and 2 and are tabulated in Table 1.

It may easily be concluded from the table that the first order specific rate is function of peroxydisulphate ion as well as N-methyl acetamide concentration; it decreases with an increase in peroxydisulphate ion concentration and is governed by the expression

$$-\log k = 2.325 + 6.80 [S_2O_8^{2-}]$$

Fig. 1. Effect of $K_2S_2O_8$ concentration : $[CH_3CONHCH_3] = 0.05M$; $[AgNO_3] = 0.001M$, Temp. = $35^\circ C$.

Fig. 2. Effect of $\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_3$ concentration : $[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]=0.01M$; $[\text{AgNO}_3]=0.001M$; Temp. = 35°C .

TABLE 1

$[\text{AgNO}_3]=1 \times 10^{-3}M$		Temp. = 35°C		
$[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]$ Conc.	$[\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_3]$ Conc.	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k \times 10^3 = (k_1 - k_2)$ min ⁻¹
0.0050M	0.050M	6.06	1.70	4.36
0.0075M	0.050M	5.62	1.44	4.18
0.010M	0.050M	5.33	1.34	3.99
0.015M	0.050M	5.00	1.21	3.79
0.020M	0.050M	4.61	1.15	3.46
0.010M	0.010M	3.03	1.34	1.69
0.010M	0.025M	3.84	1.34	2.50
0.010M	0.010M	4.70	1.34	3.36
0.010M	0.050M	5.90	1.34	4.56

whereas it increases in a linear manner with an increase in N-methyl acetamide concentration and obeys the following relationship :

$$k = 1.08 \times 10^{-3} + 8.0 \times 10^{-2} [\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_3]_0$$

The above findings are similar to those obtained in oxidation of alcohols⁵⁻⁷ and dimethyl formamide^{1,1} by peroxydisulphate ion.

Effect of AgNO_3 concentration : The effect of silver nitrate has been studied by carrying out the experiments at different concentrations of AgNO_3 as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

$[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]=0.01M$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCH}_3]=0.05M$		Temp. = 35°C	
$[\text{AgNO}_3] \times 10^3 M$	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹ = $(k_1 - k_2)$
1.00	5.33	1.34	3.99
1.50	6.14	1.98	4.16
2.00	6.87	2.46	4.41
2.50	7.80	3.20	4.60
3.00	8.69	3.90	4.79

The catalytic effect of AgNO_3 is similar to that obtained in dimethyl formamide^{1,1} and propionamide^{1,2} reactions and following relationship holds good :

$$K = 3.60 \times 10^{-3} + 0.40 C_{\text{Ag}^+}$$

Effect of Temperature : The reaction was studied at four different temperatures for the evaluation of various energy parameters, the results are summarized in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Temp. in $^\circ\text{A}$	$K \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	Temp. coefficient	Energy of activation (ΔE) in K cal mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor $A \times 10^7$ in lit mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) in E.U.	Free energy (ΔG^\ddagger) in K cal mole ⁻¹
303	2.52			10.82	-24.23	23.80
308	3.98	2.51	17.32	10.53	-24.23	23.93
313	6.33	2.44	17.08	10.55	-24.24	24.04
318	9.70			10.69	-24.22	24.17
Mean		2.47	17.30	10.65	-24.23	23.98

E graphically came out to be 16.35 K cal mole⁻¹.

ΔH^\ddagger was calculated by plot of $\log \frac{k}{kT/h}$ vs $(1/T)$ on the basis of

$$k = \frac{kT}{h} \times e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/RT} \times e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/R}$$

The value of ΔH^\ddagger which came out to be 16.47 K cal mole⁻¹ has been used in the above equation to calculate ΔS^\ddagger .

The large negative entropy of activation is indicative of incorporation of water molecule (reaction mechanism, equation 2) and the involvement of two oppositely charged ions (reaction mechanism, equation 1) during the course of reaction^{1,1-1,2}. Further it may be mentioned that the energy of activation and negative entropy of activation for this reaction are of the similar order of magnitude as that for the oxidation of dimethyl formamide^{1,1} and propionamide^{1,2}.

Salt effect and specific effect of ions : In order to study the dependence on ionic strength (μ) the reaction was studied at various concentrations of the salt K_2SO_4 . It was observed that the specific rate constant decreases by the increase in ionic strength. Further a plot between $\log k$ vs $\mu^{1/2}$ was found to be a straight line which establishes a negative salt effect on the reaction. The specific effect of K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ and Zn^{++} ions were studied. The results of these studies are tabulated in Table 4.

TABLE 4

$[K_2S_2O_8]=0.01M$, $[CH_3CONHCH_3]=0.05M$, $[AgNO_3]=0.001M$
Temp. = 35°C

Salt added	Conc.	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹	$k \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹ = ($k_1 - k_2$)
—	—	5.33	1.34	3.99
K ₂ SO ₄	0.04M	2.98	0.88	1.90
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.04M	3.11	0.98	2.15
H ₂ SO ₄	0.04M	3.39	1.09	2.30
ZnSO ₄	0.04M	3.49	1.15	2.34

It is evident from above data that of all the ions under study K⁺ has strong specific inhibitory effect on the rate.

Effect of Allyl Acetate : To study the effect of organic compounds on reaction rate, the allyl acetate was chosen. Fig. 3 consists of the effect of traces of allyl acetate on the rate of N-methyl acetamide reaction and self decomposition of peroxydisulphate ion. It is obvious that the inhibitory effect on the two reactions is of similar order of magnitude indicating that the radical(s) involved in the self decomposition and N-methyl acetamide oxidation would have been the same.

Fig. 3. Effect of allyl acetate :
 $[K_2S_2O_8]=0.01M$; $[AgNO_3]=0.0001M$; Temp. = 35°C.

Mole ratio and Products of reaction : The mole ratio between peroxydisulphate ion and N-methyl acetamide, after taking into consideration the decomposition of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ comes out to be 2 moles of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ to one mole of $CH_3CONHCH_3$. The presence of acetic acid throughout the course of reaction was detected by conventional tests. On the other hand, the presence of methyl amine, formaldehyde, formic acid and ammonia (detected by Reiglers reagent¹⁵) was observed in the early stages only and after 24 hours none of these were found

to be present, probably due to their oxidation to N_2 , CO_2 as final products of the system. The presence of NH_3 , $HCHO$ and $HCOOH$ indicates that CH_3NH_2 formed in the beginning suffers decomposition to methyl-enimin ($CH_2=NH$) and later into NH_3 , $HCHO$, $HCOOH$. The formation of methyl-enimin as intermediate product in the preparation of primary amines by reactions of aldehydes and ketones with ammonia has also been mentioned by Morisson and Boyd¹⁶.

Discussion

The first order behaviour of reaction w.r.t. $S_2O_8^{2-}$, zero order w.r.t. $CH_3CONHCH_3$ linear relationship between specific rate and Ag^+ , strong specific inhibitory effect of K⁺, mole ratio 2 : 1 between $S_2O_8^{2-}$ and $CH_3CONHCH_3$ and N_2 , CO_2 and H_2O being the final products, suggest that the following reaction mechanism may be possible.

It is noteworthy to mention here that the first two steps have been proposed by Bown and Margerison¹⁷ and Srivastava and Singh¹¹⁻¹² in silver catalysed oxidation reactions by peroxydisulphate ion.

Applying the steady state treatment to the radicals Ag^{+2} , SO_4^- ; $\cdot\text{NH}_2$; $\cdot\text{NH}$; $\cdot\text{OH}$; $\cdot\text{H}$ and HCOO . and also keeping in mind that the rate of disappearance of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is governed by process (1), the rate of reaction has been simplified to

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+]$$

where k is the experimental first order rate constant.

The above equation is in conformity with experimental results and the mechanism elucidated.

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